

Fabric Equiangular Spiral Antenna

Justin A. Dobbins*, Andrew W. Chu, Patrick W. Fink, Timothy F. Kennedy,
Gregory Y. Lin, Michael A. Khayat, Robert C. Scully
NASA – Johnson Space Center, Houston, TX 77058, USA

Introduction

As wireless technology becomes more integrated with everyday activities, interest in wearable antennas continues to grow [1-5]. Researchers have created a variety of such antennas, with the most popular being wearable microstrip patches and PIFAs [1-5]. Wearable antennas have been constructed using woven conductive fabrics or by bonding copper conductors directly to a fabric substrate, often involving either simple conductive patterns or labor intensive processes for more complex patterns. A semi-automated process for creation of fabric-based RF and microwave components was developed at NASA – Johnson Space Center. This process, which makes use of pre-woven conductive fabric, was used to create several devices, including patch antennas and microstrip lines. Here, to demonstrate a complex conductive pattern, we present a fabric equiangular spiral antenna and compare performance with the same antenna created using conventional techniques and materials. The wideband nature of the spiral antenna is well suited to spacesuit applications, and is naturally more resistant to impedance control or detuning issues that may arise from flexure of other types of antennas.

Materials

The woven conductive fabric used in this study, Nora, was obtained from Shieldex Trading of Palmyra, NY. Nora has a nylon base and is plated with silver, copper, and nickel. Its thickness is 0.06 mm with a manufacturer’s surface resistivity specification of 0.03 Ω /square. A polyester cloth, obtained from a retail fabric store, was selected to serve as the base for the conductive pattern. In lieu of a material pedigree and property values, measurements were made to obtain an estimate of the material properties of the cloth.

Fabric measurements were conducted between 0.82 – 4.0 GHz using a Damaskos, Inc. Model 08 Thin Sheet Dielectric Tester with Damaskos “Cavity™” software on an Agilent E8362B network analyzer. This measurement configuration uses a rectangular cavity to measure the in-plane component of ϵ and $\tan \delta$ for thin (< 3 mm) samples with $\epsilon < 10$. The polyester cloth was measured in the Damaskos cavity with the following results.

material	thickness	ϵ'	ϵ''	$\tan \delta$
polyester cloth	0.43 mm	1.99	0.138	0.070

The Damaskos software requires the user to input the sample material thickness. Since an accurate measurement of the material thickness was difficult, we obtained a bound on the permittivity error by entering a range of thicknesses centered at the nominal value, as shown below.

Δ thickness	thickness	ϵ'	ϵ''	$\tan \delta$
-0.13 mm	0.3 mm	2.4	0.196	0.082
+0.13 mm	0.56 mm	1.8	0.107	0.061

This fabric was found to be considerably more lossy than other fabrics tested in this study. Whereas we found this material to significantly degrade performance when used as a microstrip substrate, it does not noticeably affect the performance of the spiral antenna as shown in the next section.

Fabric Spiral Antenna

A fabric equiangular spiral antenna was constructed of Nora conductive fabric. The two arms of the spiral were applied to the polyester cloth in a semi-automated process. An RG-178 coaxial cable was used to feed the antenna with the outer conductor soldered to one spiral arm. The inner conductor of the coaxial cable was soldered to the opposing spiral arm, and a short length of dummy cable was also soldered to this opposing arm to maintain symmetry as demonstrated by Dyson [6]. For comparison, a similar antenna was constructed using etched copper spiral arms on a 1.52 mm thick Rogers RT/Duroid 5880 substrate.

VSWR was measured with an HP 8510 network analyzer and simulated using EIGER with PEC radiating elements [7-8]. Figure 1 shows a comparison of measured and simulated VSWRs with the reference plane at the antenna feed.

Figure 1. (a) Fabric equiangular spiral (60.9 mm outer radius) and (b) Measured and simulated VSWRs.

Figure 2 shows right-hand circularly polarized gain and axial ratio pattern comparisons. Measurement and simulation reference planes were located at the antenna feed, and the impedance mismatch for the conventional copper antenna was used to offset EIGER directivity patterns.

(a) Gain – 2 GHz

(b) AR – 2 GHz

(c) Gain – 3 GHz

(d) AR – 3 GHz

(e) Gain – 4 GHz

(f) AR – 4 GHz

Figure 2. (a-f) Radiation patterns and axial ratios for measured fabric, copper, and simulated PEC spirals.

Conclusion

A fabric equiangular spiral has been shown to perform comparably to a conventional copper-clad laminate spiral of the same design. Although the fabric antenna was supported by a fairly lossy substrate, and the conductivity of the arms is less than that of copper, the effects of these loss mechanisms appear to be negligible. It should be noted that the balun, which extends the length of the arms, is characterized by a higher conductivity than the conductive fabric and may be mitigating possible losses. Planned future work includes development of a fabric balun structure in order to enhance flexibility and to implement fabric interconnects.

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